
CONUS ADAMI, WILS 1988 — SPECIES OR SUBSPECIES?**R. M. Filmer*****Introduction**

Study, during the last five years, of *Conus adami* WILS, 1988 leads to the conclusion that *C. adami* is a subspecies of *Conus trigonus* REEVE, 1848.

Turnbull (1977) and Singleton (1986) described but did not name *C. adami* trawled by prawn boats operating out of Darwin. Later the same year the latter sent the author some specimens obtained from shrimp trawlers operating out of Darwin, Northern Territories, Australia. Study of these specimens initially led to the conclusion that they represented a new *Conus* species. Later a number of specimens which appear to be intergrades, were studied, leading to the conclusion that subspecific status is more appropriate.

Systematic part

Conus trigonus adami subsp. nov.

Description: Shell obconic very light in weight. Adult size 100 mm (reported by Turnbull) to 35 mm (Paratype no. 2) most being 50 to 70 mm. Shoulders broad, acute (about 74 degrees) and almost carinate. Bodywhorl converging sharply base very narrow. Sides display, slight bulge somewhat below shoulder, some concavity towards base.

Spire nearly flat, sometimes depressed, with eight flat to concave post nuclear whorls with raised edges, inside edge raised more than outer, except on last whorl. Spire whorls sculptured on inner two thirds with many fine spiral cords and some variable, curved and radially aligned striae, sutures clearly defined, colour white with some pale brown-tan flecks, apex mamillate, raised and flesh coloured.

Bodywhorl shiny with few spiral grooves at the base, (some specimens have two or more punctate spiral grooves just below the shoulder (Plate 1, figs. 7, 8 10, 11), and many curved axial striae, some stronger growth marks and often damage scars. Ground colour white. Most specimens marked with some interrupted spiral rows of brown-tan dots and dashes of variable intensity, some fused into axial stripes. Some specimens possess two tan-orange interrupted spiral bands. Some have heavier blotches or more pronounced rows of spiral dots and dashes. Below the shoulder are a few brown-tan axial squiggles. Base unmarked.

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Aperture broadish and constant in width being squarely angled at shoulder. Interior white and transparency of the thin shell allows the exterior brown-tan marks to show through. Lip thin and strongly curved in outline. Columella slightly twisted with a slight fold.

Periostracum smooth and transparent with distinctive hairlike projections along spire (Plate 1, fig. 9). TURNBULL describes the periostracum as "thin, brown and opaque and bearing fine, well-spaced ridges on the body whorl". No ridges were evident on specimens examined. WILS does not mention ridges, nor do they appear in his photographs. Neither the animal nor the operculum were available for study.

Habitat: In deeper water, depth and nature of sea bottom unknown.

Distribution: *C. trigonus adami* occurs in the Arafura Sea, between northern Australia and Indonesia. WILS reports the type material from "Off Cape York, Gulf of Carpentaria, N. Australia". LOCH reports Australian Museum specimens from Arafura Sea and West of Nassau River Gulf of Carpentaria, Queensland. The locality stated for specimens obtained from Taiwanese trawlers is suspect.

Discussion: *C. trigonus trigonus*, *C. trigonus adami* and the 'intergrades' are compared in table 2. The principal differences between the two subspecies are: *C. trigonus adami* flatter spire, more, finer spiral cords, shoulder broader more acute, base narrower (graph 1) columella fold less pronounced. Shell much lighter in weight (graph 2). Some specimens display spiral grooves below the shoulder (Plate 1, figs 7, 8, 10, 11).

Periostracum much thinner, more transparent with hairlike projections at the sutures (Plate 1, figs 7, 8, 9), (*C. trigonus trigonus* has spiral rows of tufts on the bodywhorl and lacks hairlike projections at the sutures).

C. trigonus adami is not known from shallow water, whereas *C. trigonus trigonus* commonly occurs in shallow water, even intertidally. In addition *C. trigonus adami* has not so far been obtained from North West Australia, where *C. trigonus trigonus* is common.

Some specimens obtained during the 1970's from Taiwanese trawlers, most likely from the north of Australia, where these trawlers were very active, are close to *C. trigonus trigonus* but broader at the shoulder and lower spired. These specimens seem to be 'intergrades'. Until more information is available subspecies status is more appropriate for *C. adami*.

C. angasi TRYON, 1883 and *C. advertex* GARRARD, 1961 are much smaller, less elongate, heavier, straighter sided species, with more spiral cords, whorls not raised at the inner edge, less clearly defined sutures, a more pronounced columella fold and a periostracum lacking raised hairs.

C. sugimotonis KURODA, 1928 and *C. whiteheadae* DA MOTTA, 1985 are much heavier, more elongated, convex sided, with sharper apices.

C. tribblei WALLS, 1977 and *C. queenslandis* DA MOTTA, 1984 are much heavier, elongated shells with fewer, stronger, spiral cords on the spire whorls.

C. visagenus KILBURN, 1974 has a keeled shoulder, stronger spiral cords, a pale violaceous interior and is much smaller and heavier.

C. ione FULTON, 1938 and *C. sieboldii* REEVE, 1848 are narrower with concave spire whorls lacking spiral cords.

C. luciae MOOLENBEEK, 1986 is much narrower, heavier, elongated and has a stepped spire with beaded early whorls.

Material studied: Listed in table 1.

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TABLE 1 MATERIAL STUDIED — DIMENSIONS AND WEIGHTS

Locality		Length in mm	Width in mm	L x W over 10	Weight in g	Specimen in collection of
<i>C. trigonus trigonus</i>						
Dampier	W.A.	75.1	47.7	358	35.2	R.M. Filmer
"	"	65.3	40.3	263	27.1	"
"	"	80.0	49.0	392	40.7	J.F. Singleton
Port Hedland	"	56.2	34.1	192	12.9	R.M. Filmer
"	"	51.3	32.3	166	13.2	"
"	"	69.0	43.0	297	23.2	J.F. Singleton
Onslow	" +	50.3	30.5	153	11.9	R.M. Filmer
"	"	38.6	25.6	99	6.9	"
Cawden	"	51.8	31.5	163	11.9	"
Broome	"	50.0	31.8	159	11.0	"
"	" +	42.8	27.3	117	7.2	"
Weerdie Isl.	"	48.1	30.6	147	12.9	"
Thevenard Isl.	"	74.0	47.5	352	34.5	D. Roeckel
"	"	62.5	39.0	244	23.0	"
Darwin	N.T. +	41.3	26.0	107	6.5	R.M. Filmer
"	"	37.0	22.8	84	5.2	"
Uncertain **		53.6	33.8	181	13.6	D. Roeckel
" **		49.8	27.4	136	9.0	"
" **		54.1	33.3	180	13.5	"
<i>C. trigonus</i> 'intergrades'						
Uncertain **		55.1	35.9	198	12.5	ZMA
Timor Sea *		80.0	52.0	416	36.7	J.F. Singleton
" *		44.0	31.8	140	8.8	"
Uncertain *	+	44.3	29.4	130	9.2	D. Roeckel
" *		42.5	29.6	126	8.0	"
<i>C. trigonus adami</i>						
Holotype		71.7	49.6	356	17.9	IRScNB
Paratype n.º 1	0	43.2	29.5	127	—	"
Paratype n.º 2	0	35.8	27.0	97	—	E. Wils
Arafura Sea	+	74.3	48.5	360	17.6	R.M. Filmer
"	+	50.7	34.3	174	9.6	"
"	+	79.2	51.0	404	24.6	"
"		67.0	45.7	306	22.0	"
"		65.6	42.9	281	14.0	"
"		51.5	37.8	195	12.2	D. Roeckel
"		71.6	49.9	357	17.1	J.F. Singleton
"		56.0	38.0	213	11.6	"
"	0	62.8	42.3	266	—	A.J. da Motta
"	0	58.5	38.8	227	—	"
"	0	85.6	56.4	483	—	F. Turnbull
Uncertain **	+	42.3	29.7	126	6.5	R.M. Filmer

+ = Specimens figured.

0 = Specimens not examined or weighed.

* = Locality reported by Mr. Victor Wee of Singapore whose shrimp boats brought up the specimens (J.F. Singleton in litt., and D. Roeckel in discussion).

** = Uncertain locality, from Taiwanese Trawlers.

TABLE 2 COMPARISON OF DIFFERENCES

Feature	<i>C. trigonus</i> <i>trigonus</i>	<i>C. trigonus</i> 'intergrade'	<i>C. trigonus</i> <i>adami</i>
Shape			
Spire-height	low to medium	low to medium	flat or depressed
-shape	convex	slightly convex	concave
-whorls	flat to convex	flat to concave	flat to concave
Shoulders	rounded & broad	slightly rounded & broader	acute to carinate & broadest
Bodywhorl	convex & tapered	convex to straight & more tapered	straight to concave & most tapered
Aperture	widest	less wide	least wide
Lip	curved back	curved back	strongly curved back
Sculpture			
Spire-spiral cords	some strong	more & finer	many very fine
Spire-radial striae	strong	medium	fine
Bodywhorl	often with spiral cords never with grooves below shoulder some strong basal grooves	usually with spiral cords never with grooves below shoulder some strong basal grooves	never with spiral cords often with grooves below shoulder fewer weaker basal grooves
Columella	strong fold	weak fold	weak fold
Colour			
Spire	many heavy curved radial dark brown to orange stripes	some weaker curved radial tan to orange stripes	few weak curved radial pale tan to orange stripes
Bodywhorl	two broad solid dark brown to orange spiral bands usually numerous spiral rows of dark brown lines	two weak broken tan to orange spiral bands usually numerous spiral rows of tan broken lines	bare remains of two pale tan to orange spiral bands usually few spiral rows pale tan dots & dashes & some axial squiggles below the shoulder
Weight	heavy	medium	light
Periostracum	thickish with spiral rows of tufts on bodywhorl, no projections on sutures	unknown	thin with no tufts on bodywhorl, hairlike projections on sutures
Habitat	intertidal to deeper water	deeper water	deeper water
Locality	from Gulf of Carpentaria to NW Australia	Unknown, probably northern Australia	Arafura Sea to Cape York Queensland

GRAPH 1 DIMENSIONS

GRAPH 2 SIZE COMPARED TO WEIGHT

PLATE 1

- 1-2-3 *Conus trigonus adami* from Arafura Sea 79.2 x 51 mm
4-5-6 *Conus trigonus adami* from Arafura Sea 74.3 x 48.5 mm
7-8-9 *Conus trigonus adami* from Arafura Sea 50.7 x 34.3 mm
10-11-12 *Conus trigonus adami* Locality uncertain 4.2 x 29.7 mm

PLATE 2

- 1-2-3 *Conus trigonus* 'intergrade' locality uncertain 44.3 x 29.4 mm
4-5-6 *Conus trigonus trigonus* from Onslow WA 50.3 x 30.5 mm
7-8-9 *Conus trigonus trigonus* from Broome WA 42.8 x 27.3 mm
10-11-12 *Conus trigonus trigonus* from Darwin NT 41.3 x 26.0 mm

